

Dataset Identifiers

A dataset is a collection of data. The data can be one or more tables, documents or files. This diagram provides some initial guidance on selecting a dataset identifier.

This decision tree addresses inbuilt/'out of the box' functionality. Identifiers such as Handle and URN:NBN can be configured to adopt much of the functionality of DOIs but this requires technical resources.

Dataset Identifiers

A dataset is a collection of data. The data can be one or more tables, documents or files. This diagram provides some initial guidance on selecting a dataset identifier.

This decision tree addresses inbuilt/'out of the box' functionality. Identifiers such as Handle and URN:NBN can be configured to adopt much of the functionality of DOIs but this requires technical resources.

URN:NBN €

National persistent identifier infrastructure based on the Uniform Resource Name (URN), that is a Uniform Resource Identifier (URI) that uses the URN scheme as a namespace and in which the implementation is based on National Bibliographic Number for which the National Library is the Registration Agency.

Format: urn:nbn:nl:ui:13-y0h-pdg

DOI €

A Digital Object Identifier is a persistent identifier using the Handle system and is used to identify objects, based on an ISO standard. The developer and administrator of the DOIs is the International DOI Foundation (IDF). The DOI system is implemented through a federation of registration agencies, such as DataCite and Crossref, coordinated by the IDF. DataCite is a membership organization which provides services to create, find, cite, connect, and use datasets and other research objects. Crossref is a membership organization which provides content registration services to assign DOIs and register metadata for journal articles, books, conference proceedings and preprints.

Format: 10.17026/dans-x5j-6ruy

Handle

The Handle system (www.handle.net) was developed by Corporation for National Research Initiatives (CNRI). It is a framework for managing digital information and provides a naming scheme for unique identifiers, called 'Handles'. A resolution system translates the handles into location-related data. A centrally administered registry service manages the resolving naming authorities. A Handle consists of two parts: a naming authority and a unique string that identifies an object. The ePIC consortium provides PID services for the European research community for the allocation and resolution of persistent identifiers.

Format: 11304/69544d65-3ef6-45ca-84a6-04152313872e

€ Membership/Subscription Fees

All services with this symbol charge some sort of membership or subscription fee for full access to the service. Full access can include features such as minting the PIDs and API access. These fees can vary depending on the service and the type of organisation who wishes to use them. Many of the PID services which do not have membership or subscription fees require more technical resources from your organisation to set up and maintain the service.

For more information on dataset identifiers

- FREYA Knowledge Hub page on Identifiers for Publications and Data
<https://www.pidforum.org/t/pids-forpublications-and-data/297>
- D3.1 Survey of Current PID Services Landscape
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3554254>

Copyright of Members of the FREYA Consortium. Created by members of the FREYA Consortium. This work is made available under a Creative Commons CC BY License <https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>
The FREYA project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 777523.